

THE RELATIONSHIP OF NOCARIOUS LESIONS OF THE HARD TISSUES OF TEETH WITH THE STATE OF THE HEPATOBILIARY SYSTEM

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Abstract. *An analysis of the literature data showed that the prevalence of non-cariou lesions of hard dental tissues ranged from 3.22% to 23.45%. It has been established that the formation of pathological abrasion of hard dental tissues, abfraction and wedge-shaped defects are the result of an excessive drop in occlusal load. Violation of the morphological and chemical structure of the enamel and dentin of the teeth plays a role in the pathogenesis of non-cariou diseases, which leads to abrasion. Of great importance in the development of non-cariou diseases of hard dental tissues are somatic diseases, especially the pathology of the liver and endocrine system, as well as environmental, occupational, alimentary and social factors.*

Keywords: *non-cariou lesions, prevalence, etiology, pathogenesis, erosion, wedge-shaped defect, pathological erasure.*

Introduction.

Diseases of hard dental tissues are widespread among the population of Russia and other countries of the world. Non-cariou lesions of the hard tissues of the teeth is an extensive group of dental pathology, which includes many nosological forms that are similar to each other in terms of manifestation and genesis [4, 8, 13, 20]. The average prevalence of non-cariou lesions ranges from 10% to 23% in people who are not employed in occupationally hazardous industries. At the same time, increased enamel abrasion in the structure of diseases varies from 9,2% to 18,0%. Erosion - 0,9–2,6%, Wedge-shaped defects - 2,6-5,0%, various forms of hypoplasia - 1,9-4%. Fluorosis affects from 30,0% to 90.0% of the population in various endemic, unfavorable areas [4, 13, 16, 19]. It is important to take into account the fact that a number of areas of the Amur Region are endemic in terms of the content of fluorine in natural sources. Thus, the amount of fluorine in drinking water in the city of Shimanovsk averages 3,7 g/l, in the Arkharinsky district this figure approaches 4,8 g/l, which indicates a high level of saturation with free fluorine [13].

According to some authors, the prevalence of non-cariou lesions occurring after teething has increased significantly in recent years. So, in 74% of patients, non-cariou lesions were detected: enamel erosion was 47,2%, wedge-shaped defects - 19,3%, pathological abrasion of teeth - 21,8%, dentin hyperesthesia - 67,3% [14]. A significant increase in the prevalence of erosions, wedge-shaped defects and combined forms of tooth damage, different opinions about the causes of the disease indicate the relevance of the topic and serve as the basis for this study [1, 6, 7, 9, 14].

Methodology.

The problem of diagnosis, treatment and prevention of non-cariou lesions of the teeth continues to be one of the most urgent and unresolved problems of modern dentistry [14]. Non-cariou lesions of the hard tissues of the teeth is an extensive group of dental pathology, which includes many nosological forms that are similar to each other in terms of manifestation and

genesis [19]. The causes of these diseases are not well understood. There are different views on the pathogenesis of non-carious lesions of the teeth, arguments are given in favor of one or another theory of their occurrence.

The problem of diagnosis and treatment of wedge-shaped defects of hard tissues of the tooth is due to its prevalence, lack of unity of views on treatment tactics and insufficient coverage in scientific and medical literature. If much attention is paid to the study of dental caries, then a few publications are devoted to the study of non-carious lesions of teeth in an adult [6, 12]. Among non-carious lesions of the teeth, a number of clinical forms of these pathological processes and diseases (increased tooth wear, fluorosis, trauma) have been studied in sufficient detail [1, 5, 6, 12, 26]. Methods for their prevention and treatment have been developed [10, 15]. In the occurrence of some other nosological forms of lesions of hard tissues of the tooth (erosion, wedge-shaped defects), there is still a lot of uncertainty, both in relation to their etiopathogenesis, and methods of prevention and treatment. One of these diseases is a wedge-shaped defect in the hard tissues of the tooth. Until now, there is conflicting information about the prevalence of this pathology of the teeth among adults of different age groups. There is no information about the features of the clinical course of wedge-shaped defects in hard tissues of the tooth in elderly and senile people.

The problem of diagnosis, treatment and prevention of non-carious diseases continues to be one of the urgent and unresolved problems of modern dentistry. Research by V.I. Kobeleva (1981) show that for 1000 surveyed residents of Moscow aged 16–60 years, 10% were non-carious lesions of the teeth. Whereas, according to WHO (1999), non-carious diseases were found in 43,5% of 12th and 41,7% of 15th adolescents. The authors' studies showed that 50% of children in Western Australia had fluorosis. According to the authors, the prevalence of fluorosis in the Moscow region (Krasnogorsk) is 97%. Tooth discoloration can also be caused by antibiotics [11]. The authors' studies have shown that the prevalence of non-carious lesions occurring after teething has increased significantly in recent years. Thus, 74% of patients had non-carious lesions: enamel erosion was 47,2%, wedge-shaped defects - 19,3%, pathological tooth abrasion - 21,8%, dentin hyperesthesia - 67,3%. According to O.V. Petrichenko (2004), dentin hyperesthesia (up to 60%) is recorded in various groups of patients.

Other foreign authors consider the bending of the tooth caused by excessive occlusal load on it to be the main cause of non-carious lesions. Scientists assign a special role to frequent and transcendental lateral loads during chewing or in the case of parafunctions of the dentoalveolar system and tongue [18, 21, 27]. The tension that occurs in the area of the neck of the tooth gradually provokes chronic fatigue in hard tissues with their subsequent destruction in this area. Enamel destruction processes can be accelerated by acid erosion [2, 11, 20, 22, 24, 29].

The modern theory, not excluding the impact of excessive occlusal loads on the tooth, explains the etiology of abfractions as a process of destruction of enamel prisms as a result of the piezoelectric effect. Under the influence of atypical occlusal loads, a bending stress develops in the tooth, which causes an electrostatic process known as the piezoelectric effect. As a result of this process, calcium ions are pushed out of the crystal lattice of calcium hydroxyapatite molecules of enamel prisms [3, 8, 17, 20, 28].

M. Braem [7] believes that defects caused by pressure on the tooth are more often observed in bruxism, as well as in patients without distal contact points of the tooth. Spectral analysis showed the direction of stress vectors in the cervical region depending on the nature of the applied

force. Under a tensile load, the resulting defect has a V-shape, under a compressive load - a C-shape [20].

The occlusal theory of abfraction explains the shape of the defect. The resulting lesion is deep, with an acute angle at the base, sometimes extending into the subgingival region [18, 29]. According to our observations, the defect may be in the form of a step or a ledge and occurs in the area of the neck of the tooth. Morphological changes occur in the enamel, because the elastic dentin is less susceptible to stress from occlusion. The magnitude of the defect depends on the degree of occlusal stress, the duration of the action of excessive occlusal forces, their direction, frequency and place of application. With prolonged exposure to atypical occlusal force, along with abfraction defects, chewing (occlusal) abrasion facets are revealed, where the parafunctional load on the tooth occurs [20]. Abfraction may be accompanied by gingival recession, but this is not its hallmark - the epithelial attachment moves apically from the site of the tooth subject to overload as a result of the resulting bending stress [11, 20].

Some authors [17, 23, 25] consider abfraction to be the phenomenon underlying the occurrence of wedge-shaped defects. In modern clinical practice, it is necessary to clearly differentiate the concepts of "wedge-shaped defect" and "abfraction defect"). In this issue, attention is paid to the diagnosis of occlusal contacts. Obviously, if supracontacts are detected on teeth with V-shaped defects and there is an overload of individual teeth and groups of teeth, then it is more correct to speak of abfraction in this case. Wedge-shaped defects (abrasion) occur more often in the cervical area, mainly on the bare part of the root and, due to the low microhardness of dentin, rapidly increase in size.

In ICD-10, in section K.03, non-cariou dental lesions such as dental erosion (K03.2) and abrasion of teeth (wedge-shaped defect) (K03.1) can be diagnosed. "Abfractional defect", which belongs to class V according to Black's classification, is not allocated to a separate group, so it is necessary to determine the place of this term. This type of non-cariou lesion can be classified under K03.18 Other specified abrasion of teeth / Other specific abrasion of teeth. However, increased attention to this type of defects dictates the need to separate them into independent nosological forms.

Since many authors do not consider abfraction as a component of the wear of hard tissues, there is clearly not enough data from clinical and epidemiological studies to date. When analyzing the available literary sources, we did not come across published results of studies on the prevalence of abfraction defects among various population groups.

In addition, most of the studies are not representative due to the small sample size of the surveyed. As already mentioned, comparison of published data is problematic due to differences in indicators and terminology.

In 2010, as part of an epidemiological survey of the adult population of the Republic of Belarus, employees of the Department of General Dentistry of BelMAPO conducted a survey of the population in all regions of the Republic of Belarus and the city of Minsk. The main key groups of the adult population were examined: 18, 35-44 years, 65 years and older. A total of 2184 people were examined.

Non-cariou lesions were determined by visual examination of the mouth and entered into the map, received and analyzed occlusionograms in the central occlusion.

Results and discussion.

The results of an epidemiological survey of residents of the Republic of Belarus (2010) and their comparison with data from previous years showed the high incidence and prevalence of non-

carious lesions that develop after teething (abrasion, abfraction defects, abrasion, erosion). Currently, this pathology is observed in $40\% \pm 1,76$ middle-aged people (35–44 years old, the number of examined 767 people) and in $4,21\% \pm 0,74$ 18-year-olds (the number of examined 736 people).

The prevalence of combined lesions among 35–44 year olds was 24,8%. Moreover, a combination of two types of non-carious defects occurred in $23,45 \pm 2,4\%$ of cases, a combination of three types - in $3,9 \pm 1,1\%$. The intensity varied from 0,27(1,16) to 2,23(4,03) affected teeth.

As the data of the epidemiological survey of the population show, the prevalence of non-carious lesions increases from $4,21 \pm 0,74\%$ at a young age (18 years) to $40 \pm 1,76\%$ among the adult population aged 35–44 years. The prevalence and intensity of tooth wear increases with age: from $0,95 \pm 0,36\%$ to $13,95 \pm 1,25\%$, 0,02(0,2) - 0,44(1,39) and from $2,72 \pm 0,6\%$ to $16,3 \pm 1,33\%$, 0,034(0,21) - 0,44(1,46), respectively.

The intensity of abfractions in the structure of non-carious lesions also increases with age from 0,45(0,92) to 0,64(1,6), However, among patients with non-carious lesions in the cervical area, there is a decrease in the incidence of abfractions and tooth abrasion with age: from $22,6 \pm 7,5\%$ to $19,54 \pm 2,26\%$ and $61,3 \pm 8,7\%$ to $25,4 \pm 2,5\%$, respectively. This suggests that abfraction defects are early signs of increased occlusal loading.

Conclusion.

The prevalence and intensity of combined lesions sharply increase with age: $3,22 \pm 3,17\%$ and 0,16(0,9) for 18-year-olds; $23,45 \pm 2,5\%$ and 2,23(4,03) in the group of 35–44 years, which is typical for the long-term influence of atypical occlusal loading and other pathological risk factors involved in the etiology of non-carious defects. The lack of consensus on the issues of etiology, pathogenesis, clinical manifestations requires in-depth study in order to comprehend, systematize the data and develop recommendations for its diagnosis, treatment and prevention.

REFERENCES

1. Ахмедов А. Б., Камалова Ф. Р. Modern views on the prevalence, etiology and pathogenesis of dental fluorosis in children // Журнал стоматологии и краниофациальных исследований. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 1.
2. Ахмедов А.Б. Проблемы профилактики и лечения некариозных поражений зубов в детском возрасте // «Профилактика стоматологических заболеваний» сборник материалов республиканской научно-практической конференция. Ташкент 23-24 март 2018 г. С.11-12.
3. Баратов Ф. и др. Профилактика зубочелюстной аномалий и деформаций у детей и подростков бухарской области // Stomatologiya. – 2015. – Т. 1. – №. 4 (62). – С. 56-59.
4. Борисова Э.Г., Лепехина Л.И., Кумирова О.А. и др. Некариозные поражения тканей зуба // Международный журнал прикладных и фундаментальных исследований. – 2014. – № 3. – С. 149–150.
5. Боровский Е.В. Кариес зубов: препарирование и пломбирование / Е.В. Боровский. – М.: Стоматология, 2001. – 144 с.
6. Боровский Е.В. Эрозия твердых тканей зуба / Е.В. Боровский, П.А. Леус // Стоматология. – 1971. – № 3. – С. 1–5.
7. Браем Марк. Пришеечные поражения, вызванные давлением на зуб // Fenestra. – 1995. – № 4. – 27 с.

8. Гаффоров С. А., Ахмедов А. Б. Тиш қаттиқ тўқимасининг кариес бўлмаган жароҳатлари этиологияси, даволаш ва профилактикаси //Доктор ахборотномаси. – 2019. – Т. 2. – С. 148-153.
9. Гаффоров С.А., Ахмедов А.Б. Научные взгляды на этиопатогенез, лечение и профилактику некариозных поражений тканей зубов (обзор литературы) // Stomatologiya. – 2019. – №2. – С. 79-82.
10. Гланц С. Медико-биологическая статистика / С. Гланц. – М.: Практика, 1999. – 459 с.
11. Гольдштейн Р. Эстетическая стоматология. Второе издание. Том 2. 2005,
12. Грошиков М.И. Некариозные поражения тканей зуба / М.И. Грошиков. – М.: Медицина, 1985. – 172 с.
13. Дмитриева К.М. Эндемические заболевания Амурской области // Амурский исследовательский журнал. – 2014. – № 4. – С. 50.
14. Журбенко В. А. и др. Распространенность некариозных заболеваний полости рта в современной стоматологии //Международный журнал прикладных и фундаментальных исследований. – 2015. – №. 4-2. – С. 301-300.
15. Иорданишвили А. К. Заболевания эндодонта, пародонта и слизистой оболочки полости рта //М.: МЕДпресс-информ. – 2008. – С. 13–18.
16. Луцкая И.К., Марченко Е.И., Чухрай И.Г. Эстетическое пломбирование некариозных дефектов твердых тканей зуба // Современная стоматология. – 2012. – № 1. – С. 29–31.
17. Макеева И. М. и др. Электронно-микроскопическое исследование твердых тканей зуба при клиновидных дефектах //Стоматология. – 2009. – Т. 88. – №. 4. – С. 39-42.
18. Маунт Г. Минимальная интервенция в стоматологии. Кариозные поражения локализации 3 типа // ДентАрт. – 2006. – № 3.
19. Окушко В.Р., Рябцева И.М. Флюороз зубов – маркер интоксикационной гипоплазии // Современная стоматология. – 2016. – № 1. – С. 40–43.
20. Ронкин К. Связь абфракций с дисфункцией височно-нижнечелюстного сустава // Dental Market. – 2010. – № 5. – С. 9–11.
21. Хельвиг Э. и соавт. Терапевтическая стоматология. 1-е изд., 1999.
22. Akhmedov A. B. Diagnostic value of amino acid composition of blood in children with erosion of dental tissues //International confedrence on social and humanitarian research. Cologne, Germany. – 2021. – С. 257-258.
23. Akhmedov A. B., Razhabov A. A. Use of glassionomer cement for filling temporary teeth after gentle preparation //European journal of modern medicine and practice. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 12. – С. 56-58.
24. Akhmedov A.B., Ishanova M.K., Qodirova M.T., Dosmukhamedov E.Kh., Utesheva I.Z. Prevalence, prophylaxis and treatment principles of primary teeth erosion in children // International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation, 2020, Vol. 24, Issue 04, pp. 2073-2078.
25. Bahodirovich A. A. Evaluation of the diagnostic value of osteocalcin level and alkaline phosphatase activity in the early diagnosis of erosion of hard tissues of teeth in children //International journal of health systems and medical sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 5. – С. 215-219.
26. Bahodirovich A. A., Utkirovna R. D. Modern views on the prevalence, etiology and pathogenesis of dental fluorosis in children //Middle European Scientific Bulletin. – 2021. – Т. 18. – С. 287-293.

27. Brackett W. W. et al. Two-year clinical performance of a polyacid-modified resin composite and a resin-modified glass-ionomer restorative material //Operative dentistry. – 2001. – T. 26. – №. 1. – C. 12-16.
28. Gafforov S. A., Akhmadaliyev N. N., Akhmedov A. B. The role of the hormonal background of the organism on growth and development of oral cavity tissues //Toshkent tibbiyot akademiyasi axborotnomasi. – 2019. – №. 4. – C. 21-24.
29. Lee W. C., Eakle W. S. Possible role of tensile stress in the etiology of cervical erosive lesions of teeth. J. Prosthet Dent. 1984; 52: 374–380.